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MODERNIZATION OF EDUCATION DEVELOPMENT IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract - The development of the education system is one of the most important tasks in Uzbekistan. The article analyzes and reveals the education system created in Uzbekistan, taking into account the requirements of the time and high standards, which opened up the widest opportunities for the young generation of the country in realizing their potential.

Keywords - Education, Education System, Continuity, Priority of Education, National Orientation, Availability, Quality, Competitiveness.

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of the education system in Uzbekistan is very important. Because education serves to further develop the socio-economic life of the country. This requires further development of existing innovations in education.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The following scholars have considered modernization of education development in the republic of Uzbekistan in their research: Mirziyoyev Sh.M. [6].

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this research, we used of methods of scientific observation, abstract logical reasoning, statistical and systematic analysis, as well as selective observation and social survey.

IV. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

As you know, providing citizens with high-quality and affordable education is a task that largely determines the development of society and its future. In this sense, in our country, among the few in the world, this area is not only viewed as one of the

most important directions of state policy, but in fact it demonstrates tremendous success. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev signed a decree on the approval of the Concept for the development of the higher education system until 2030.

Achievements are obvious, first of all, in the field of training personnel that meet the most modern requirements. Undoubtedly, the effective implementation of goals and objectives in this part of social policy largely depends on two main factors. This is, first of all, sufficient funding, as well as a solid regulatory framework that establishes the laws of the system's functioning and highlights its main vectors of development.

Speaking about the legal foundation of the education system, it is necessary to highlight the National Program for Personnel Training adopted in 1997 and the State National Program for the Development of School Education approved in 2004. These basic documents were developed through a thorough analysis of domestic and world experience and are aimed at forming a new generation of specialists with modern knowledge, high general and professional culture, creative and social activity, the ability to independently navigate in various situations, to set and solve problems.

In 2016, the country's budget allocated 14 trillion 419.3 billion soums to the education sector, which is 16.6% more than the same indicator of last year. The funds go both to the salaries of teachers (today about 390 thousand teachers work only in the public education system), and to the reconstruction and construction of buildings of schools, universities, lyceums, colleges, as well as their equipping with modern technical means.

In particular, in the near future it is planned to open 52 new facilities and overhaul in 14 higher educational institutions of the country. To date, almost 10 thousand schools, 1556 lyceums and colleges, more than 70 universities have been overhauled, and work in this direction continues, as evidenced by serious financial support and all the outside attention of the state to this direction. Over the years of

independent development in Uzbekistan, a radical reform of the entire field of education was carried out, which made it possible to form an effective education system.

Today, various forms of retraining and advanced training of personnel are being created, which make it possible to maintain professional knowledge at the level of modern science and technology. Such education provides the development of cognitive abilities, the ability to form creative thinking in the training of qualified specialists, social activity and a spiritually rich personality. The basic principles of education development are:

- priority of education - development, prestige of knowledge, education and high intelligence;
- humanization of education - the disclosure of a person's ability and satisfaction of his educational needs;
- humanization of education - the formation of an aesthetically rich worldview, high spirituality, culture and creative thinking among students;
- democratization of education - expanding the independence of educational institutions in the choice of methods of teaching and upbringing, transitions to a state-public system of education management;
- the national orientation of education lies in its organic unity with national history, traditions and customs, preservation and enrichment of the culture of the peoples of Uzbekistan;
- the continuity of training and education;
- identifying gifted youth, creating conditions for knowledge, developing their talent.

The strategic goals of the public education system are:

- increasing the spirituality of high-quality secondary education in accordance with the requirements of innovative development of the economy, advanced international experience and modern needs of society;

- unlocking the potential of each student;
- the development of human capital as the main factor that determines the level of competitiveness of a student in the labor market and the country as a whole. Such a modernized education system should promote the development of students' analytical skills, the ability to apply academic knowledge in real life, "soft" or "flexible" skills such as teamwork, leadership, etc.;

In addition, in the long term, the following priority tasks are envisaged:

- Qualitative renewal of the content of the continuous education system, as well as training, retraining and advanced training of professional personnel;
- Creation of a system for purposeful work with gifted and talented children and youth;
- Providing spiritual and moral education, the formation of a physically developed and healthy child;
- Improvement of teaching methods and their implementation in the educational process;
- Improving the quality of educated services provided to children with disabilities;
- Widespread introduction of modern methods and directions of out-of-school education in the upbringing of young people and ensuring their employment in an innovative economy.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, over the years of independence, fundamental structural and substantive reforms have been carried out, affecting all levels and components of the education system, which are aimed at ensuring its compliance with the country's long-term objectives and interests, the requirements of the time, as well as world standards. An appropriate legal framework for reforming this area has been created, which has determined as a priority the growth of investment in human capital, the training of an educated and intellectually developed generation, which is

the most important value and a decisive force in achieving the goals of democratic development, modernization and renewal, and stable economic growth.

Higher education coverage is planned to be increased to 50% by 2030. The coverage of graduates of secondary educational institutions with higher education in 2030 should reach 50%. The President approved the concept for the development of the higher education system. Within the framework of the concept, more than 70 targets have been approved, which are planned to be achieved by 2030. Among them, an increase in the coverage of graduates with higher education from the current 20% to 50%, the number of non-state universities, including on the basis of public-private partnerships (PPP), from 5 to 35, coverage of the credit-modular system - from 2% to 85%. To date, within the framework of the implementation of the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, special attention is paid to expanding the coverage of youth in higher education, improving the quality of education, strengthening the material and technical base of higher educational institutions. Expanding cooperation with foreign universities plays an important role in achieving the set goals.

Currently, more than 100 universities operating in our country train highly qualified personnel. Branches of leading universities of the USA, Great Britain, Italy, South Korea, Russia, Singapore, India carry out effective activities in Uzbekistan. In addition, a number of projects in the field of higher education are being successfully implemented together with financial institutions and developed countries of the world.

In order to improve the subject programs in the 2019-2020 academic year, it is planned to study in 3830 educational areas of the bachelor's degree and more than 1910 subjects in the magistracy. This year, over 2,700 bachelor's and more than 1,300 master's subjects were discussed at the Coordination Council of the ministry and recommended for the educational process. To achieve an exemplary state of Information Resource Centers (IRC) of higher educational institutions, a training

workshop was held at the Tashkent State Institute of Oriental Studies with the participation of directors of the capital IRC.

On the example of this university, the conditions for students created at the institute and the principles of software operation are clearly demonstrated. In addition, it should be noted that in accordance with the decision of the Board of Trustees of the Fund "EL-yurt Umidi" under the Cabinet of Ministers of Uzbekistan in May this year, 517 candidates who successfully passed all stages of the competition were approved by the scholarships of this fund.

V. CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

Thus, the reform of the education system is aimed at increasing the prestige of domestic science among young people and more active participation of scientists in the innovative development of the country. The effectiveness of the reform is directly related to the openness and transparency of scientific activity. In addition, the objectivity of the requirements that the three-level model of higher education imposes on the quality of the content of scientific research has been tested by the rich experience of organizing science in developed countries. The implementation of this model will allow Uzbekistan to successfully integrate into the world scientific space.

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